

A STUDY ON THE CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN POLICE AT PALAKKAD DISTRICT IN KERALA

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Abstract

Preservation of peace and protection of life and property are the basic needs in a democratic society. As a defence force, the police enjoy a lot of privileges as well as responsibilities. The country's peace and harmony vested in their hands. The employment of women in police establishments reflects not only the socio-economic advancement but also changes in the attitude towards the role of women in society. Objectives of this study are to study the challenges faced by the respondents, to study about the family support and social acceptance of women police, to study about the job satisfaction among women police. The research design of this study was descriptive in nature. SPSS software was used to analyse this study. Major findings of this study are most of the respondents are satisfied with their job and their family. Nearly half of the respondents get time to spend with their spouse. But majority of the respondents face difficulties because of their dress code and least percentage of the respondents facing some difficulties from male colleagues. The researcher is sure that empowering women police officers will plan an important role in providing a secure and harmonious society. This study concluded that though there are problems faced by the women police in general yet they are satisfied with their job.

Keywords: Preservation, Protection, Defence force, Harmonious

INTRODUCTION

Preservation of peace and protection of life and property are the basic needs in a democratic society. Since each citizen cannot assume individual responsibility for the fulfilment of these needs, various Governments have employed the police force to preserve and protect the rights and properties of citizens.

Police are Government officers who enforce the law and maintain order. In a broad sense, the term police connotes the maintenance of public order and the protection of persons and property from the hazards of public accidents and the commission of unlawful acts specifically, it applies to the body of civil officers charged with maintaining public order and safety and enforcing the law including preventing and detecting crime.

Women in policing are still, to this day, not treated as equally as men. Women police officers have always been discriminated against man. Many women advance in police work but few actually pursue it. Being in the criminal justice field wanting to pursue this career as a woman is a great challenge. Police, work to prevent crime and to protect the lives and property of the people of a community. Police man serves their communities in many ways. They patrol streets to guard against crime and to assist people with various problems. The police are often called

to settle quarrels, find lost people and aid accident victims. During floods, fires, terrorist attacks and other emergencies they help provide assistance transportation and protection for victims.

Women police

The employment of women in police establishments reflects not only the socio-economic advancement but also changes in the attitude towards the role of women in society. It was only after independence that women were appointed in the police force on regular basis in different states, after the partition of India in 1947, which brought endless misery and to appoint women police for recovery of abducted women and girls for rehabilitation.

History of women police

The need for women police was first recognized in the United States, during the first half of the nineteenth century, when "Police Matrons" were appointed in New York City in 1845, for handing of women and girls held in Police custody, by the law enforcing agency. The earliest appointment of a police woman, as distinguished from a police matron, was made in Chicago, in 1903, women police were officially employed for the first time in staff art (Federal Republic of Germany) and in 1905, a woman was given police powers in Portland, Oregon (USA), to deal effectively with problems involving girls and children. In 1910, the first regularly rated police women were appointed by the Los Angeles Police Department. The First World War provided an opportunity for women to serve as volunteer workers and part-time workers to demonstrate, in a conspicuous manner, their usefulness in police work. The Metropolitan women police was formed London in 1919 (Rao et al, 1975)

Though women are expected to work like men on equal terms, in a country like India, people's perception of their role goes beyond the regular routine job of police personnel. Women police can play a major role in social available sources hence women police were employed in maximum numbers in the lowest subordinate ranks, in keeping with the general universal trend of the police organization. The need for women police increased with the rise in number of women accused criminals and victims of crimes such as rape, kidnapping, sexual harassment, dowry deaths etc.

The Indian Police Service (IPS) has been appointing women in the IPS Cadre at par with men. These women are expected to have the same qualifications and training as is expected of their male counterparts. Similarly, the other police-based services such as the border Security Force, CRPF, CISF, NSG, Railway Protection Force and The Home Guards all recruit women in various capacities.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

We have a very efficient police force in the country who have excelled themselves in not only tackling crime but also in ensuring peace and harmony. Women police have also significantly contributed in this regard. This study helps to enable all ranks of women police in the Palakkad to share the experience and challenges of the work. That will provide a wholesome and holistic approach to the problems which are to be tackled by them. Unfortunately, the incidence of

crimes against women has quite significantly gone up and the role of the police, particularly women police has become quite crucial in such cases. Nobody can understand a women's problem better than another woman. Therefore, the role of women police becomes all the more critical women kind including crime particularly in the present-day world there is no much emphasis on reformative approaches rather than retributive ones.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mangaleswaran R (2012) conducted a study on Adjustment problems among the Married Women Police Personnel. He pointed out that, "The nature of job of police is very complex to work. It requires fullest dedication and commitment on employing people. While working they face several hardships from both in job as well with family life. Though there might be many problems they face on day -to- day life, but there can be numerous adjustment problems they faced, that to the married women. The data was collected from all the married women police personnel available during the time of data collection in Tiruchirappalli District. The findings show that almost in all dimensions and overall adjustment problems, the respondents have high level of adjustment problems. There is a need for counselling and recreational centre exclusively for women police personnel.

Lina Sadekar and Shami Pai, (Nov 2011), conducted a study of workplace stress among working women- the cause-and-effect analysis, the pointed out that, The American Institute of Stress estimates that work- related stress costs American businesses about \$300 billion every year in lower productivity, higher absenteeism, low turnover rate, alcoholism and medical costs. Today, chronic work-related stress is not just an American affliction. In India, over half of the call centre employees feel so stressed out by the tough working conditions that they end up quitting. Stress is an adaptive response to a situation that is perceived as challenging or threatening to a person's well - being. Stress is a negative consequence of modern living. People are stressed because of over work, job insecurity, information overload and the increasing pace of life not merely confined to paid employment.

Mashkoor (2010) conducted a study on Problems of Working Women. He pointed out that, working women have to face problems just by virtue of their being women. Working women here are referred to those who are in paid employment. Social attitude to the role of women lags much behind the law. This attitude which considers women fit for certain jobs and not others colors those who recruit employees. Thus, women find employment easily as nurses, doctors, teachers the caring and nurturing sectors, secretaries or in assembling jobs- the routine submissive sectors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives of the study

- To study the social demographic profile of the respondents.
- To study the challenges faced by the respondents.
- To study about the family support and social acceptance of women police.
- To study about the job satisfaction among women police.
- To study the attitude of women police and their family members towards profession.

The universe selected for the study was from some police stations at Palakkad, from them 50 samples were selected by the researcher using non probability Sampling in which Purposive Sampling method was used. The researcher adopted the questionnaire method for data collection.

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on their type of family

Sl. No.	Family	Frequency	Percentage
1	Joint	39	65
2	Nuclear	21	35
	Total	60	100

The above table shows 65% of the respondents are living in joint family. And 35% of the families live in nuclear family.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on their satisfaction of job

Sl. No	Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
1	Never	2	3
2	Rarely	2	3
3	Sometimes	6	10
4	Always	49	84
Total		60	100

The table shows that 3% of the respondents are never satisfied with their job, 3% of the respondents rarely satisfied with their job, 10 % of the respondents sometimes satisfied with their job and 84% of the respondents always satisfied with their job.

Graph 1: Distribution of respondents based on their colleagues support in the profession

It shows that 72% of the respondents always get support from their colleagues, 25% respondents sometimes get support from their colleagues, 1% of the respondents were rarely get support from their colleagues, and 2% of the respondents never get support from their colleagues.

- Nearly half of the respondents (48.3%) have about 10 years' experience and belong to 30-35 years age group.
- Nearly half of the respondents (48.3%) feel that male superior sometimes show partiality. Reason is the male officers are not having confidence to trust women police officers.
- Few women police officers feel pressure while performing their duty especially night patrolling. Night patrolling is the most difficult duty for them. Reason is most of the women police officers are living in rural areas.
- Nearly half of the respondents (41%) get help from their colleagues sometimes.
- Majority of the respondents (60%) are involved in all the duty (station duty, traffic duty, night patrolling). All the police officers have to do all the duty irrespective of gender.
- Majority of the respondents (76.7%) face difficulties because of their dress code.
- Nearly half of the respondents (46.7%) are satisfied with their family. They can manage work-life balance in a proper way.
- Majority of the respondents (71%) husband are satisfied with their job. Reason is some of the women police officers are managing their household activities doing

- More than half of the respondents (53%) are never rejected from the relatives and friends because of their profession.
- Majority of the respondents (81%) are satisfied with their job.
- Majority of the respondents (66.7%) feel that their job is a good fit for based on their qualification/skills.

DISCUSSION

Though Police job is stressful for women, but they are satisfied with their family and job also. Majority of the respondents feel that their job is a good fit for based on their qualification. Half of the respondents were rejected from their friends and relatives because of their profession. People are considering police job is not fit for women. Because of dress code women police officers are faced difficulties during duty time. Most of the women police officers get support from their colleagues. Women police officers are involved in all the duties like station duty, patrolling etc. with pleasure. The country's peace and harmony are vested in their hands. Because of that, their services are most important to every country.

CONCLUSION

The study made by the researcher makes clear about the nature of work of women police, occupational stress level and stress management attitude of the family members towards the job, and attitude of the women police towards the work. The researcher is sure that empowering women police officers will play an important role in providing a secure and harmonious society. Their exemplary performance motivates and inspires many women to join the police force; best wishes to all the women police personnel for success in their mission. Hence it's concluded that though there are problems faced by the women police in general yet they are satisfied with their job. Hats off to the police community in general for their crucial support to the community.

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